

Supplementary Information

Triaxial 3D-Channeled Soft Optical Sensor for Tactile Robots

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Fig. S1: Activation level of the three photoreceivers shown with separate channels when varying X, Y, and Z of the applied displacement on the sensor for the three compared designs: channels with $\varnothing_{Ch} = 2\text{mm}$, channels with $\varnothing_{Ch} = 4.4\text{mm}$, and Bulk.

Fig. S2: Activation level of the three PRs shown as channels in the HSV space when varying X, Y, and Z of the applied displacement on the sensor. Different patterns for different tactile locations can be identified in the three tested scenarios. Changes in Hue, Saturation, and Value reflect changes in the first, second and third PR, respectively.

Fig. S3: Normalized fraction of rays arriving to the walls while exerting a force up to 3 N for stiffness levels ranging from 0.56 kPa to 3.56 kPa.

Fig. S4: Fabrication of the bulk prototypes. The external shell is cast (1) and inserted in the mold (2). The black spot and PDMS are poured and let cure in sequence.

Fig. S5: Experimental setup for indentation tests integrating: (A) three orthogonal manual micrometric translation stages; (B) one servo-controlled micrometric translation stage for z-motion; (C) two perpendicular servo-controlled micrometric translation stages for xy-motion; (D) sensor prototype; (E) a triaxial load cell connected to (F) a plate probe to evenly touch the surface of the sensor.

Fig. S6: Average trials for z indented from 0.25 mm to 2 mm while the indenter was moved in the xy plane with the angle from 0° and 345° .

Fig. S7: Covariant (r, t) and orthogonal (x, y) reference frames, in blue and red, respectively. $\theta = 7\pi/6$ is the angle between the two axes of the covariant reference frame, and γ is the angle between the x and r axes. A point P can be expressed as (r_P, t_P) in the covariant reference frame and as (x_P, y_P) in cartesian coordinates.

Algorithm 1 Sensorized Robotic Hand Controller. The algorithm initializes communication with sensors and motors. It dynamically responds to external commands via UDP sockets and monitors forces to detect object grasping. Real-time adjustments based on finger angles and forces promote object manipulation guided by a PID controller.

Initialize Serial, UDP sockets, PID controller, and motors.

Initialize Set control gains and motor positions.

while True **do**

Receive *new_command* from UDP socket

Receive *force_data* *new_command* from Serial

if *new_command* is open **then**

 Reset variables

else if *new_command* is catch **then**

if no contact established **then**

 Gradually close the fingers

else if *release_grasp* **then**

 Gradually open fingers to initial positions

else

if contact angle out of range **then**

 Position \leftarrow PID controller using *force_data*

else

 Set *release_grasp* to true

Video S1: Demo of the 3D-channeled soft optical sensor. Dynamic loads are applied to the sensor, whose real-time response is shown in terms of raw signals of the three PRs, moduli of F_z , F_{xy} (N), and the angular direction α of \hat{F}_{xy} ($^\circ$). Static loads with 5 g, 10 g, 50 g and 100 g are subsequently applied to the sensor.

Video S2: Sensor integration into a robotic hand with deformable fingers mounted on a UR5e. The hand successfully grasps a tape roll, a slippery cylinder, and a baker. The hand state and closure are adjusted based on force data.